

THE EFFECT OF MATRIX PROPERTIES ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF
MAGNESIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Tensile and fracture toughness tests have been carried out to examine the effect of matrix composition on mechanical behaviour of magnesium composites. Chemically pure (CP-Mg) magnesium and AZ91 magnesium alloy with approximately 9.5 wt. % Al and 0.4 wt. % Zn were reinforced with δ -alumina short fibres by melt infiltration techniques. The results of mechanical tests show that alloying elements improve tensile strength of AZ91 composites at a relatively higher fracture toughness values compared with the properties of CP-Mg composites. These are related to the effect of alloying elements on properties of matrix and fibre/ matrix interface and fibres. Low fracture toughness of CP-Mg composites is a result of decohesion of fibre/matrix interface due to the low interfacial strengths. Simple rule of mixture strength analysis, modified for the discontinuous and random orientation of the reinforcement have been used to predict the composite strengths. A good agreement between experimental and theoretical calculated strength was found in the case of AZ91 composites. However, the predicted strength of CP-Mg composite is lower compared with experimental strength being obtained.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Magnesium Alloy; Magnesium/Alumina; Characterization/Mechanical Properties/Fracture

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre, whisker and particle reinforcement of magnesium alloys have exhibited an improvement in physical and mechanical properties. However, metal matrix composites also indicate some limitation, particularly low fracture related properties, which limit the use of these materials in an extend range of structural applications. The purpose of recent studies were to examine the factors influencing the mechanical behaviour of magnesium matrix composites [1,2]. The effect

of type and volume percent of reinforcement, as well as the influence of fabrication routes have already been evaluated. The effects of matrix properties on mechanical behaviour of magnesium composites are the subject of the present investigation. The squeeze casting techniques were used to produce the MMC's. Tensile and fracture toughness tests were carried out to interpret the influence of matrix composition on mechanical properties of magnesium composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The materials chosen for this study were a commercially pure magnesium (99,8% Mg) and an AZ91 magnesium alloy with approximately 9.5 wt.% Al, 0.4 wt.% Zn. δ -alumina short fibres of 3 μm mean diameter and length of $\approx 150 \mu\text{m}$ with 2000 MPa strength were used as reinforcement. Plates of metal matrix composites with 35-40 mm thickness were prepared by conventional squeeze casting techniques. The fibre volume fraction was set to 0.1, 0.15 and 0.2. For comparison unreinforced material in plates of 35 mm thickness have also been produced by the same squeeze casting conditions. Cylindrical specimens of 5 mm diameter and 25 mm gauge length were used for the tensile tests. By a strain rate of 0.5 mm/min cross head speed strain was monitored via an extensometer affixed to specimens surface. Load-deflection plots were recorded using an Instron 1195 universal testing machine. Short rod specimens of 20 or 25 mm diameter were used in the fracture toughness tests. The chevron notch of the short rod specimens were approximately in the same fibres orientation as by tensile specimens. Load-displacement-curves were recorded at cross head speed according to the tensile tests. After testing, the fracture surfaces of the tensile and fracture toughness tests specimens were examined in a scanning electron microscope.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Metallography Specimens taken from the squeeze cast plates were prepared for optical microscopy. A representative three-dimensional micrograph of AZ91+15 vol.% δ -alumina composite shown in Figure 1 revealed on random planar distribution of the short fibres. It can also be seen that the fibres were almost uniformly distributed without any cluster formation. The microstructure of the matrix in composites was found to be different from this of the unreinforced material obtained under similar squeeze casting conditions. A reduction in grain size have been observed in composite (Figure 2 a and b). It appears that reinforcements act as effective substrates for nucleation of matrix which may also be referred to the proper wetting of the fibres by solidification process. In addition fibre/matrix interface serves as a proportions site for segregation of lamellar and massive $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ compound. An example of such precipitation in the case of AZ91+15 vol.% Al_2O_3 fibre have been shown in Figure 2 c. In agreement with above observations increasing volume fraction of reinforcement results in still finer microstructures.

2.2 Tensile Behaviour The tensile tests evaluations represented in Figure 3 indicate that AZ91-composites exhibit higher yield and tensile strength at all volume fractions of reinforcement compared with those of CP-Mg matrix composites. However, it is also obvious from the data of

FIGURE 1. Three-dimensional micrograph of AZ91 + 15 vol% alumina composite showing the almost random planar distribution of the reinforcement

FIGURE 2. Micrographs of AZ91 materials
 a) Unreinforced alloy,
 b) Composite with 15 vol% alumina fibre,
 c) As b) showing preferential location of fibres in lamellar $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ compounds.

this figures that the fibre reinforcement had greater effect on the improvement of the tensile properties of CP-Mg matrix. At the same time the reinforcements decrease the tensile ductility as measured by elongation to failure of both matrices (Figure 3c). However, the imbrittlement effects of reinforcement on CP-Mg matrix were more pronounced than by AZ91 matrix. In general, the properties of a metal matrix composite are dependent on the properties of the matrix, the reinforcement and the interface between matrix and reinforcement. Alloying of matrix may influence substantially these properties. In the case of magnesium alloy AZ91 alloying elements Al and Zn strengthen the matrix by solid solution. The zinc additionally improves the matrix strength by precipitation hardening through the formation of GP-zones, $MgZn'$ or $MgZn$ precipitates [3,4].

FIGURE 3. Tensile properties at room temperature of magnesium composites as function of the fibre content.
 a) Yield strength,
 b) Ultimate tensile strength,
 c) Elongation to fracture.

A roughly thicker reaction zone have been observed by AZ91 composites compared with CP-Mg composites (Figures 4a and 4b), which may be referred to the additional effect of alloying elements. The reaction products were frequently identified as MgO in both materials by microdiffraction. The formation of MgO from Al_2O_3 and Mg according to thermodynamic calculations is possible if magnesium concentrations 4 to 8 percent exceeds [5], a condition which both CP-Mg and AZ91 simply satisfy. Due to the lack of any alloying elements in the region of interface and similarity of production conditions it is suggested that only the solidification behaviour is responsible for the formation of thicker reaction zone in alloyed magnesium matrix composites [6,7]. Whereas CP-Mg melt solidified almost congruent, alloyed magnesium melt experiences a larger solidification intervals. This results in longer contact time between reinforcement and highly reactive liquid matrix leading to form thicker reaction zone. On the other hand decreasing fibre diameter as a result of thicker reaction zone, causes the degradation of the fibre strength. The lower effect of the reinforcement on yield and tensile strength improving observed in the case of AZ91 composites may be explained by this mechanism.

The strength of discontinuous randomly oriented fibres array reinforced metal matrix have frequently been determined using the modified rule of mixtures [8,9]:

$$\sigma_C = c \cdot \sigma_f \cdot v_f \left(1 - \frac{1}{21}c\right) + \sigma_m (1 - v_f)$$

FIGURE 4. SEM fractographs showing the morphology of fibre/matrix reaction zones
 a) Composite with CP-Mg-matrix,
 b) Composite with AZ91-matrix.

where σ_c is the composite strength, σ_f is the strength of the fibres, V_f is the volume fraction of fibres, l_c is the critical transfer length of the matrix at fracture of the composite, C is an empirical factor describing the inefficiency of reinforcement due to a distribution of fibres orientation. Assuming that the load on a given fibre is due only to the shear stress at the fibre-matrix interface, the critical fibre length l_c can be defined by [10]:

$$\frac{l_c}{d_f} = \frac{f}{2\tau}$$

where d_f is the diameter of fibre and τ is shear strength at the fibre-matrix interface, which for the purpose of simplifying the calculation assumed to be γ_{ym} , the shear yield strength of the matrix equivalent to one half of the matrix yield strength σ_m . With the typical properties of δ -alumina short fibres and experimentally determined tensile properties of AZ91 and CP-Mg produced by squeeze casting the strength composites have been calculated using above modified simple ROM with $C = 3/8$ (for the approximated two dimensionally oriented fibres distribution in present case). Table 1 lists the results of such calculation and values of composites strength obtained experimentally.

While the systems show good agreement between the modified ROM calculation and the experimentally determined strength of AZ91 composites, a major disagreement is observed in the case of CP-Mg composites. Similar differences have also been obtained between the experimental and theoretical strength of CP-Al- and Al-alloys composites [8,11]. It appears that this disagreement comes more probably from the value of matrix strength, σ_m , which by calculation have been taken as a constant and equal to the yield strength of the unreinforced materials. Obviously the matrix strength in composites depend on the microstructural changes and level of residual stresses created due to addition of fibres reinforcement [9,12]. In order to predict the strength

TABLE 1 EXPERIMENTALLY AND THEORETICALLY DETERMINED STRENGTH OF CP-MG AND AZ91 COMPOSITES

Composites	σ_c (MPa)	
	Theoretical	Experimental
AZ91 + 10 vol. %	219.0	222.0
AZ91 + 15 vol. %	243.7	254.6
AZ91 + 20 vol. %	268.0	295.0
CP-Mg + 10 vol. %	74.7	164.0
CP-Mg + 15 vol. %	91.8	210.0
CP-Mg + 20 vol. %	108.8	249.0

of CP-Al reinforced with discontinuous δ -alumina fibres from the simple ROM the matrix property σ_m has been modified by multiplication with an empirical constant $c^* = 2$ [8]. In the present study a good agreement between experimental and theoretical data for CP-Mg composites is obtained by using the value of $C^* = 3$. The physical significance of this empirical constant has to be intensively studied by future work. The effects of matrix properties on tensile behaviour of composites were also pronounced at elevated temperatures. Figures 5 a, 5 b, 6 a and 6 b represent the tensile tests results at elevated temperatures up to 300°C for the various fibre contents. The results indicate that AZ91 composites revealed higher tensile yield and tensile strength for all reinforcement fractions at testing temperatures compared with the same of CP-Mg-composites. In an earlier study [1] a fibre matrix debonding of AZ91 composites at temperatures above 100°C have been observed.

FIGURE 5. Effect of the temperature on the yield strength of CP-Mg and AZ91 composites for various fibre content
a) CP-Mg
b) AZ91

FIGURE 6. Effect of the temperature on the ultimate tensile strength of CP-Mg and AZ91 composites for various fibre content
 a) CP-Mg
 b) AZ91

As a result the influence of reinforcement on composites strength was decreased at testing temperatures above 100°C. Considering this the observed differences in composite strength at elevated temperatures may be referred mainly to the differences between CP-Mg and AZ91 matrices behaviour at elevated temperatures. Obviously CP-Mg matrix exhibits lower strength than AZ91 matrix at elevated temperatures.

2.3 Fracture Toughness and Fractography The values of fracture toughness of unreinforced matrices and composites tested by short rod method are presented in Figure 7. The fracture toughness of both CP-Mg and AZ91 alloys decreases as a result of reinforcement. However, the fracture toughness of AZ91 composites average approximately 70 percent of the matrix alloy and the fracture toughness of CP-Mg composites ranges only approximately 50 percent of unreinforced matrix. This fracture toughness behaviour agrees with the tensile ductility results. A comparison of the fracture morphology of specimens may demonstrate the differences in

FIGURE 7. Results of the fracture toughness tests for CP-Mg and AZ91 alloys and composites.

fracture behaviour of both types of composites. No major differences have been observed by fracture surface appearance of specimens with fibre which were randomly orientated in loading direction. The specimens of both types of composites failed in a flat manner and fibres were broken flush with exception of occasionally little fibre pull out by CP-Mg composites (Figures 4a and 4b). In the case of nearly planar oriented fibres to the loading direction the fracture of AZ91 composites specimens occurred through the fibres (Figures 8a and 8b) and the specimens the CP-Mg composites failed along the fibre/matrix interface (Figures 9a and 9b). It appears, that the decohesion of the fibre/matrix interface as a result of lower interfacial strength in the case of CP-Mg composites is the cause of marked change in the fracture related properties compared with fracture behaviour of AZ91-alloy matrix composites.

FIGURE 8. SEM fractographs of CP-Mg + 15 vol% alumina fibre composites

FIGURE 9. SEM fractographs of AZ91 + 20 vol% alumina fibre composites

3. CONCLUSIONS

Magnesium matrix composites can be produced successfully by squeeze casting independent of matrix composition and volume fraction of discontinuous alumina-fibres. The alloying elements effect the matrix properties and the formation of fibre/matrix interface under the same production conditions. A relative thicker reaction zone at the interface fibre/matrix has been observed for the AZ91 composites.

The reinforcement improves yield and tensile strength of the alloys. AZ91 composites reveal higher strength compared with CP-Mg composites. However, the magnitude of the reinforcement effect on strength is higher for CP-Mg composites. This is referred to degradation of fibres, a result of a stronger reaction between fibre and matrix of AZ91 composites. At elevated testing temperature AZ91 composites reveal likewise higher tensile strength. The reinforcement decreases tensile ductility of the alloys. The tensile ductility is higher in the case of CP-Mg composites.

The modified simple rule of mixture analysis can be used to predict the composite strength. A good agreement between experimentally and theoretically determined strength was found with a simplifying assumption.

The reinforcement decreases the fracture toughness of the composites. However, the fracture behaviour of CP-Mg composites is more substantially effected by reinforcement. Fractography reveals generally a mixed mode fracture. In addition the fracture surface of CP-Mg composites exhibits frequently decohesion of fibre/matrix interface as result of low interfacial strength. It is suggested that the crack formation due to the decohesion of the fibre/matrix interface is the mean cause of low fracture related behaviour of CP-Mg composites

4. REFERENCES

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